

Interpreting Reflective Teaching as a Crucial Means of Developing Teacher Education: an Analysis to Discover a Teacher as Self-observer

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ABSTRACT : The present article is dealt with reflective teaching as a means of developing teachers' professionalism. Teaching is a dynamic, creative, exploratory and self-observable process in which teachers encounter with a group of learners. Reflective teaching reminds us that it is a struggle to discover, a journey to tread on the untrodden. Reflective teaching suggests that experience alone is insufficient for professional growth, but experience coupled with reflective teaching can be a powerful impetus for teacher development.

Keywords : Reflective teaching, self-observation, Teacher development, constructivist approach, language teaching.

1. Introduction

Teaching is unquestionably an assorted but helping profession which depends on exploratory relationship between the teacher and the learner and this mutual relationship ultimately produces an efficacious outcome. It seems appropriate to consider in this respect how teachers view of themselves as teachers, particularly as exemplified by the following statement: "Effective teachers create learning atmospheres which are cognitively and affectively expanding;

learning atmospheres which enable the learner to become a more adequate and knowledgeable person". (Pine and Boy, 1977). Teaching is essentially a personal expression of the self. Learners realize the personal and innovative structure of the teacher long before they feel the impact of the intellectual content offered by the teacher. This noticeably has particular implications with regard to teachers' views of self-efficacy since a teacher who lacks innovative self-awareness will surely find it

impossible to build the same to others. Hence, the need to develop an innovative -cum-independent approach and take responsibility for the entire teaching/learning process within the classroom has become an important demand of the time which we, the teaching community, ought to respond.

Underlying any approach to the pre-service or in-service teacher development of second language teachers is a conception of what good teaching is and what the essential knowledge and skills of teachers are. Second language teaching is often viewed from a very limited perspective – that of the act of teaching. Consequently much of the literature on second language teaching mainly deals with teaching methods. If students fail to learn well, it is assumed to be the fault of the method, or the teacher. Very often we used to forget that teaching as an exploratory process is different from the approach to teaching seen in many teacher preparation programmes or language teaching programmes. Thus, methodology is not something fixed, a set of rigid principles and procedures that the teacher must conform to. Rather, it is a dynamic, creative, exploratory and self-observable process that begins anew each time the teacher encounters a group of learners. Alternative paradigms have also been proposed, such as that of Fanselow in his book “*Breaking Rules*” (1987), which might be described as a “beyond-methods’ perspectives. In Fanselow’s approach, teachers are encouraged to develop their own methods of teaching through exploring alternatives to conventional prescriptions for good teaching and the most effective pedagogical alignment related to this approach is reflective teaching.

Reflection has become something of a buzzword in recent years and it is associated with self-observation. Many people feel that it is important for teaching in general and language teaching in particular, where reflection is an important part of the teaching/learning process. Reflection simply means becoming aware of the self, of the context and everything connected with it, including how we are teaching and how we teach best. Reflection refers to a mobility flowing from within or process in which an experience is revisited in the present context, usually in relation to a broader canvas. It is a response to bygone experience and involves conscious recall as a basis for decision-making. Reflective teaching is a journey moving beyond a primary concern towards a more exploratory, a more deeper purposes. This journey, notwithstanding, reminds us about constructivist approach to teaching/learning paradigm that takes place within a cognitive framework. A constructivist view of motivation centres around the premise that each individual will act on his/her internal disposition and use his/her personal attributes in unique ways. This is the message that the reflective teaching offers.

Most of us would agree that a second or foreign language is learnt not so much by direct instruction in its rules as by using it in meaningful contexts, especially when the students’ experience, interests and knowledge of the world are involved. According to current developments in cognitive psychology, information is stored in memory in two forms: declarative knowledge, i.e., what we know about a given topic, and procedural knowledge, i.e., what we know how to do. Apart from the two categories, what is important in reflective teaching is to expand the boundaries of procedures through the process of self-observation, a peep into the self. Many

approaches can be employed if one wishes to become a critically reflective teacher, including developing one's thinking skill, observation of oneself and others, team teaching, and exploring one's view of teaching through writing.

The term 'reflective teaching' was popularized by Cruickshank et al. and Zeichner, though both of them defined the term differently. To Cruickshank et al., reflective teaching refers to 'an opportunity to consider the teaching event thoughtfully, analytically and objectively', an alternative means of achieving goals. While to Zeichner, a reflective teacher is one who assesses the origins, purposes and consequences of his or her work at all levels. Both of them agreed that the purpose of reflective teaching is to engender good and critical habits of thought. That is why reflection is acknowledged to be a key component of many models of teacher development.

Teacher development is possible through reflective teaching. The description by Kemmis (1986) best describes the meaning of reflection:

"Reflection is not just an individual, psychological process. It is an action-oriented, historically-embedded social and political frame, to locate oneself in the history of a situation, to participate in a social activity". Thus reflection is more than thinking. In order to be an effective reflective teacher, one has to move away from the 'how to' questions, which have a limited utilitarian value, to the 'what' and 'why' questions. Question started with 'what' and 'why' gives us a certain sense of power over our teaching. In reflecting on 'what' and 'why' questions, we begin to exercise control and open up the possibility of transforming our everyday classroom life. The process of control is called 'critical reflective teaching' It is expected in

reflective teaching that the teachers will observe their actions in relation to the historical, social, and cultural context in which our teaching is actually embedded. The cycles of activity containing the five elements of Mapping (what do I do as a teacher?), Informing (what is my intention as teacher?), Contesting (How do I come to be this way?), Appraising (How should I teach differently?), and Acting (what and how shall I now teach?) are represented in figure 1

Teacher development through reflective teaching

Figure 1. The elements of a cycle for the process of reflective teaching. (Adapted from McTaggart and Kemmis 1983; Smyth 1987)

Reflective teaching through the process of self-observation refers to a systematic approach to the self-monitoring, self-evaluating and self-managing of one's behaviour. In order to improve professional performance, however, teachers need feedback about their teaching. Self-observation is a means of getting feedback. Here teachers are able to acquire skills of self-inquiry and critical thinking. Self-observation is carried out by the three major approaches in teaching – personal reflection, i.e., the use of diary, self-reporting, and audio or video recordings of a lesson.

Paulo Freire (1972) once told that reflection without action is verbalism: action without

reflection is activism – doing things for their own sake. The process of reflective teaching creates immediate situations where the text becomes part of the class’s experience. That is why reflective teaching is effective in all learning situations, as it aims at developing the students’ competence in many fields. Simultaneously, it develops communicative competence, creative competence, and cultural competence. Here we find a close resemblance between constructivist view of teaching and reflective teaching. Both the views introduce to the notion of teachers’ horizons of understanding which are constantly in the process of formation but which are constructed within traditions, larger frames of reference which provide shared ways of making sense. No two teachers and no two teaching situations are ever the same. For the constructivist, both the content of any lesson and the way in which it is offered are part of the person of each individual teacher. An important component of a constructivist approach to education is for teachers to become conscious of what their own beliefs and views of the world are, which lead us into the notion of the reflective practitioner. The differences among teachers, therefore, are not simply a question of whether they are good or bad, competent or incompetent; what is most important how teachers view themselves as teachers. The logical fallacy that one who teaches is a teacher, can never be taken into consideration.

Conclusion

Reflective teaching, like most teacher-based forms of self-inquiry, is not an easy process. It involves a paradigm shift in emphasis in our thinking and acting. Teaching is a struggle to discover, a journey to tread on the untrodden. The present picture related to classroom

teaching is simply discouraging as teaching, now-a-days, has become mostly information-laden, as a result, learners are suffering from a grotesque disease, namely, paper-thirst or readymade answer-thirst instead of wonder-thirst for their immediate pursuit. In this running-track, they are gradually retreating from their ability to think, to imagine and we, the teaching community, are slowly becoming desensitized. So-called “learner-friendly teachers” may think not to carry the unhygienic mantle that would surely deprive the innocent learners in the long run. A reflective approach to teaching involves changes in the way we usually perceive teaching and our role in the process of teaching. Reflective teaching suggests that experience alone is insufficient for professional growth, but that experience coupled with reflection can be a powerful impetus for teacher development. Becoming reflective extends beyond ourselves, making possible a similar form of self-inquiry in learners. They will be allowed to break the chains of alienation imposed on them, not only by the routine of everyday experience, but also by the oppressive ignorance of language in the society into which they have been inducted. Let a new culture be emerged - not the culture of silence but the culture of imagination, a culture to dream. A sip of optimism will not be irrelevant in this respect.

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